

ELECTROSPINNING OF COMPOSITE FIBERS WITH CORE-SHELL STRUCTURE AND SELF-HEALING PROPERTIES

Fenghua Zhang¹, Zhichun Zhang¹, Yanju Liu², and Jinsong Leng¹

¹Centre for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, People's Republic of China

Email: fhzhang_hit@163.com; zczhang@hit.edu.cn; lengjs@hit.edu.cn

²Department of Astronautical Science and Mechanics, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, People's Republic of China

Email: yj_liu@hit.edu.cn

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we successfully investigate the composite fibers with core-shell structure via electrospinning method and their self-healing properties using heat as source. Core-shell fibers are prepared by coaxial electrospinning method using thermoset epoxy as core solution and thermoplastic PCL as shell solution (20 wt%). The morphology of composite fibers is characterized through scanning electron microscopy, which shows the resultant fibers are uniform and smooth, and the diameter range is from 1 μm to 2 μm . Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) that is carried out to analyse the structure of composite fibers proves epoxy/PCL nanofibers with core-shell structure and the diameter of inner fiber is about 300 nm to 600 nm. Comparing with PCL nanofiber membrane, the epoxy/PCL composite membrane keeps the fiber morphology after heat treatment at 60 °C. In addition, the macroscopic scratch can effectively realize self-healing process with a high speed and the fiber structure is not destroyed when the specimen is heated above the transition temperature. It is significant that these properties bring the epoxy/PCL films as functional coatings to various applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the development of materials science, an increasing number of fibers, fiber membranes, or fiber coatings are attractive. Micro- and nano-size materials, due to their excellent properties, such as large surface areas, high long slenderness ratio, and strong penetration with other matrix, and so on, are able to be used in a huge number of fields. These properties play an important role in medical engineering, textile, filtration, energy storage materials, etc.[1-5]

In recent years, coaxial electrospinning method has attracted great attention due to the easy operation process which can produce special structure and function of core-shell fibers with diameter from 10 nm to 1000 nm.[6-8] The rapid development promotes potential applications in wide fields such as, biotechnology, and optical glass fiber science, etc. For instance, some researchers have prepared the PCL nanofibers to be used in biomedicine. [9] P T Mather' group

has reported the composite system by combining PCL nanofibers with epoxy matrix to display the triple shape memory effect and self-healing properties.[10-12]

However, thermoset polymers are not be able to electrospin into fibers because of the poor spinnability. In addition, many polymers generate micro-crack or even damage, which may cause the macro-failure without immediate and effective repairing. In order to solve these issues, we design a kind of composite fibers system with core-shell structure through co-electrospinning of epoxy into fibers as core layer and polycaprolactone (PCL) as shell layer and healing agent. This type composite fiber has lots of advantages to be used in functional coatings and biomedical device and so on in the future. [13-15]

In this paper, PCL as shell layer and epoxy as core layer were electrospun into fibers by coelectrospinning technology. This composite system was characterized using SEM, TEM and optical microscope to analysis the morphology, as well as the structure. Self-healing behavior was demonstrated from micro perspectives.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Polycaprolactone (PCL) was purchased from Perstorp UK limited in pellet. The dichloromethane (CH_2Cl_2) and dimethylformamide (DMF) were used as the solutions. Epoxy-based shape memory polymer was fabricated in our group as described in the previous report. [16] The chemicals used in this experiment need no future purification.

2.2 Preparation of Fiber Membranes

CH_2Cl_2 and DMF were mixed together with a volumetric proportion of 4:1. PCL was dissolved in the mixed solvent with concentration of 20 wt%. The polymer solution was stirred on a magnetic stirrer at room temperature until well mixed.

Electrospinning equipment contains three parts, including high power, collector, and a syringe. As can be seen in Figure1a, this is the experimental setup we used to prepare the nanofibers. The difference between coelectrospinning and traditional electrospinning is that coaxial electrospinning has a special design of its spinneret. Figure 1b shows the compound needle which is composed of two capillary tubes. A compound Taylor cone, at the tip of needle, was formed during the electrospinning process. Under the right conditions, we collected the epoxy/PCL composite nanofiber membrane which is white colour, as shown in Figure 1c.

The parameter of electrospinning was that applied voltage was 12kV, the distance between needle tip and collector was 18 cm and the speed rates of PCL and epoxy were 0.01 mm/s and 0.0005 mm/s, respectively. The composite nanofibers were cured at 50 °C for more than 70 h in the oven.

2.3 Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Quanta 200F) was carried out to observe the micromorphology of composite epoxy/PCL fibers.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM, FEI, Tecnai G2 F30) was performed to analyse the core-shell structure of epoxy/PCL composite fibers.

Optical microscope (Keyence VHX-900) was used to characterize the morphology and structure of electrospun fiber membranes.

Figure 1: Photos of the electrospinning: (a) electrospinning equipment, (b) coaxial needle, (c) epoxy/PCL composite fiber membrane.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 SEM Analysis

During the coaxial electrospinning, the core and shell fluid should have the appropriate feed rate. As shown in Figure 3, the SEM morphology of epoxy/PCL composite fibers electrospun from the solution with a PCL loading of 20 wt% is investigated. Fixing the feed rate of PCL at 0.001 mm/s, the feed rate of epoxy was adjusted to 0.0005 mm/s, respectively. SEM images indicated that the resultant fibers produced from core-shell needle were well separated and no beads. All the fibers were short and the reason for this was that epoxy was not able to be electrospun. The shell liquid was drafted by the electrical field, and the core solution was stretched by frictional force, which may lead the core-shell structure more completeness.

Figure 2: SEM images of epoxy/PCL composite fibers.

3.2 Structure of cross-section

The core-shell structure of epoxy/PCL composite fibers was characterized by SEM image. The specimen was directly electrospun on copper grids for test without any other treatment. The SEM image of cross-section of co-electrospinning fibers is shown in Figure 3, which clearly demonstrates the electrospun composite epoxy/PCL fibers with core-shell structure. The core material was epoxy, whose diameter was about 300 nm and the shell material was crosslinking PCL with a diameter of 1600 nm. An obviously boundary between PCL and epoxy-based polymer could be observed, which indicated the composite exhibiting core layer and shell layer in one fiber. The reason for this was that two viscous polymeric liquids were injected into the core and shell capillaries, respectively.

Figure 3: SEM image of cross-section of electrospun epoxy/PCL composite fiber with core-shell structure via coaxial electrospinning method.

3.3 Self-healing behavior

The optical microscope was carried out to observe the microstructures of pure PCL fibers and electrospun epoxy/PCL composite fibers after heat treatment in the oven. As shown in Figure 4(a), it is clear that the pure PCL film produces a lot of pores when it is heated in the oven at 60 °C and the fibrous structure disappears. However, it can be seen in Figure 4(b) that the image of epoxy/PCL composite fibers can still maintain the fiber structure after heating treatment at 60 °C, the results of which indicates that the epoxy-based polymer in the composite fibers shows fiber morphology and plays an supportive role. It is significant to research the two different types of polymers, including thermoplastic and thermosetting polymers, which have an increasing number of potential applications in many areas, especially in coating, and so on.

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Figure 4: Optical microscope images of electrospun fibers with heat treatment under 60 °C: (a) is PCL fibers and (b) is epoxy/PCL composite fibers, respectively.

Self-healing is an important behaviours of polymer coatings and fibrous coatings. As shown in Figure 5(a), this photo displays the optical microscope images of the electrospun epoxy/PCL composite fibers which is heated at 60 °C. In addition, it was clearly observed that a crack was generated on the surface of the membrane by cutting. It is also shown in Figure 5(b), the crack in Figure 5(a) disappears after heating again at, the results of which show excellent self-healing

properties. The epoxy/PCL composite fiber films, due to this performance, can be used as functional coatings in a number of fields.

Figure 5: Optical microscope images of electrospun fibers with heat treatment under 60 °C: (a) is the image of epoxy/PCL composite fibers with a crack and (b) is the image of epoxy/PCL composite fibers after self-healing, respectively.

4 CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, a composite fiber system epoxy/PCL, fabricated through co-electrospinning, was obtained, the structure of which was core and shell two layer including epoxy and PCL polymers. The resultant fibers showed excellent self-healing performance. The strategy not only obtains the thermoset polymer epoxy fibers but also achieves the self-healing performance in one composite system. It is possible leading to the ability to manipulate functionality, and it is clear that core-shell nanofiber composites will find broader applications in a host of fields.

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